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Impact of Artificial-Intelligence-Enhanced Strategy on Performance in Thermodynamics Concept among Senior Secondary School Students in Zamfara State

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Abstract:

This study investigates the impact of Artificial Intelligence Enhanced-Strategy on Performance in Thermodynamics Concept among Senior Secondary School Students in Zamfara State. Two research questions and corresponding hypotheses guided the study. The study adopted quasi-experimental research design, specifically, the pretest-posttest non-equivalent control group design using an intact class. A sample size of 140 (77 male and 63 female) chemistry students were taught Thermodynamics concept using Artificial-Intelligence Enhanced-Strategy while the control group were taught using lecture method. Chemistry Performance Test instrument was used for the study. The CPT was validated by experts and reliability index of 0.75 was obtained using Cronbach alpha reliability test. Descriptive statistics was used to answer the research question and analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) to test the null hypothesis at 0.05 level of significance. The results obtained revealed that there was significant difference between performance of students thought thermodynamics using Artificial-Intelligence Enhanced-Strategy and those taught using lecture method. It was also revealed that there was no significant gender interaction effect on the students exposed to Artificial-Intelligence Enhanced-Strategy. Thus, it was concluded that the strategy enhances students' performance and it's gender-friendly. It was therefore recommended that Chemistry teachers should adopt Artificial-Intelligence Enhanced-Strategy to improve teaching and learning outcomes.

Keyword: Artificial Intelligence-Enhanced Strategy, Performance, Thermodynamics, Chemistry

Introduction

Chemistry is a core science subject offered at senior secondary schools across Nigeria. It is also a requirement for admission into all science-based fields of study in Nigeria institutions such as medicine, pharmacy, engineering many to mention but a few. It is science field that explores the properties, composition, and reactions of matter, and the energy changes that accompany these reactions (Brown, 2020). According Levine, (2020) found as the study of the structure, properties, and transformations of matter at the atomic and molecular level. The importance of chemistry as a valuable science subject is further emphasized in the Joint Admissions and Matriculation Board

(Impact of Artificial-Intelligence-Enhanced Strategy on Performance ... Yahaya, S. U... Et. al. 2025)

syllabuses (JAMB, 2020/2021), it is stipulated that a minimum of credit pass in Chemistry is required as one of the criteria for admitting candidates aspiring to study science-related courses in tertiary institutions. Despite the important of chemistry among other science subjects and related disciplines, literature revealed that, students' performance in chemistry at Senior Secondary School Examinations (SSSCE) have been consistently poor, (Udo, 2019, Asim, 2019 & WAEC Chief Examiners' report 2015 - 2020).

Thermodynamics as one of the concepts of chemistry which is a science subject or course study in secondary schools and tertiary institutions in Nigeria. However, Thermodynamics is one of the chemistry concepts that have a very wide area which is part of Senior School Certificate Examination (SSCE) syllabus. Research findings revealed students' understanding of thermodynamics was limited, with many holding misconceptions (Kozhevnikov *et al.*, 2019). WAEC chief examiner's report from 2019 to 2023 revealed weakness areas in Secondary School Physical Chemistry like thermodynamics, Charles' law, Boyle's law and general gas equation respectively. Research found that students struggled with thermodynamic concepts, particularly energy and entropy (Krellet *et al.*, 2020). Another research finding revealed students' performance in thermodynamics was significantly lower compared to other physics topics (Ozdemir *et al.*, 2022). The performance of senior secondary school students in chemistry has been attributed to passive teacher-centered instructional strategies mostly the Lecture Method (Olorukooba, 2021, MDG's project, 2020). This implies, the lecture method of teaching is a strategy commonly used by most teachers in Nigerian schools. This method is teacher-centered and characterized by verbal one-way presentation of ideas, concepts, generalization and facts. Teacher does most of the activities in form of talking while the students are neither passive listener nor slightly involved, and they do not take care of the varied needs of the learner especially in the teaching of chemistry. As a result of this the researcher intended to use technology tool to enhance the teaching and learning process. Therefore, Artificial Intelligence-Enhanced Strategy will be use as intervention to enhance teaching and learning activities using (META AI), in order to improve the Student's performance towards learning thermodynamics as the most difficult concept in chemistry.

Artificial Intelligence (AI) is a broad field encompassing various technologies that have been developed over the past 50 years to enable machines to perform tasks traditionally requiring human intelligence, such as perceiving, reasoning, learning, and interacting (Ergen,2019). Recent curricular developments support the argument for technology integration in science education, as Nicolaou and Petrou (2023) point out. There is growing agreement that integrating artificial intelligence AI technology into education can enable teachers to support students' self-directed learning (Caswell & LaBrie, 2017), create learning communities that are collaborative, and foster creativity in understanding concepts (Connolly, Logue & Calderon, 2023).

Artificial-Intelligence Enhanced-Strategy is integrating AI technologies into teaching and learning to improve educational outcomes. It refers to the integration of AI technologies into organizational strategies to optimize decision-making and improve operational efficiency in teaching and learning process. This implies that it involves creating a comprehensive lesson plan that will be a guide to the teacher to teach student's which enabling the teacher to perform any necessary activities during

(Impact of Artificial-Intelligence-Enhanced Strategy on Performance ... Yahaya, S. U... Et. al. 2025)

teaching and learning process. Research finding revealed it enhances teacher capabilities, automates administrative tasks, and provides real-time feedback (Siemens, 2021). It also promotes adaptive learning, intelligent tutoring, and social learning analytics (Koehler, 2020). According to (Baker, 2022) observe that leverages machine learning, natural language processing, and data analytics to create personalized learning experiences. This shows that students' can have a better understanding and experience which will improve their academic performance.

The influence of gender on students' performance in Nigeria has also been a concern to educational researchers. Surprisingly, no consistent result has been obtained. Some research findings have revealed that male students achieve significantly higher than female students while some reports indicated that the reverse is the case. The studies on gender and academic performance such as that of Usman (2017) and Ibrahim (2018) showed that boys perform better than girls in terms of academic performance but a study conducted by Atadoga (2017) pointed out that there is no gender-related difference in academic performance. Therefore, from these findings, it could be introduced that the findings about the effect of gender on performance though widely spread, are inconclusive. It is for this reason that this study intends to explore the impact of Artificial Intelligence-Enhanced Strategy on Performance in Thermodynamics Concept among secondary school students in Zamfara State.

Statement of the problem

The WAEC chief examiner's report from 2019 to 2023 revealed weakness areas in Secondary School Physical Chemistry like thermodynamics, Charles' law, Boyle's law and general gas equation respectively. Record of analysis students' results in chemistry and other science subject such as physics and biology for a number of years has revealed dismal failure with chemistry being the poorest (WAEC Ann Report, 2014-2023). However, Thermodynamics is one of the chemistry concepts that have a very wide area which is part of Senior School Certificate Examination (SSCE) syllabus. Some research found that students struggled with thermodynamic concepts, particularly energy and entropy (Krell *et al.*, 2020). Another research finding revealed students' performance in thermodynamics was significantly lower compared to other physics topics (Ozdemir *et al.*, 2022).

Objectives of the Study

The main objective of this study is to examine the impact of Artificial Intelligence-Enhanced Strategy on Performance in Thermodynamics among secondary school students in Zamfara State. Specifically, the objectives of the study were to investigate:

- i. The difference between the mean performance scores of students' taught thermodynamics concept using Artificial Intelligence-Enhanced Strategy and those exposed to lecture teaching method in Zamfara State.
- ii. The mean performance of male and female students taught thermodynamics concept using Artificial Intelligence-Enhanced Strategy and those taught using lecture teaching method in Zamfara State.

(Impact of Artificial-Intelligence-Enhanced Strategy on Performance ... Yahaya, S. U... Et, al. 2025)

Research Questions

- i. What is the difference between the mean performance scores of students' taught thermodynamics concept using Artificial Intelligence-Enhanced Strategy and those exposed to lecture teaching method?
- ii. What is gender interaction effect among Secondary School Students Performance in Thermodynamics concept?

Hypotheses

H₀₁: There is no significant difference between the mean performance scores of students' taught thermodynamics concept using Artificial Intelligence-Enhanced Strategy and those exposed to lecture teaching method in Zamfara State.

H₀₂: There is no significant difference between gender interaction effects among Secondary School Students Performance in Thermodynamics concept in Zamfara State.

Research Methodology

The study adopted a quasi-experimental control pre-test and posttest research design. A pre-test was administered to both the experimental and control groups to determine the equivalence Performance in thermodynamics concept. Then a posttest was administered to all groups after the treatment to determine the effectiveness of the treatment on the concept. The total population of the study will be all the 112,577 (61,728 Males; 50,849 Females) Senior Secondary Schools Students for the 2024/2025 session in all the total of 339 Senior Secondary Schools (both public and private) offering Chemistry in Zamfara State. A target population of the study was 25,335 (16,395 Males; 8,940 Females) SS2 Students and two (2) Public-Private Secondary Schools were selected to be the sample of the study. The reason for selecting SS 2 was that, the topic thermodynamics concept was part of the second term curriculum. A sample size of 140 (77 male and 63 female) chemistry students'. The school B (40 Males: 37 Females) was represent experimental group while School A (37 Males: 26 Females) represented Control group. A simple random technique was used in selecting one (1) educational zone among the four zones by lottery method. One local government was randomly selected from the educational zone selected. Mean and standard deviation was used to answer two research questions and hypotheses using one way ANCOVA (at 0.05 significant levels). Chemistry Performance Test was the instrument used for the study. The CPT was validated by two senior lecturers at Federal University Gusau and two chemistry teachers of senior secondary schools in Zamfara State.

Presentation of Results

Research Question 1

What is the difference between the mean performance scores of students' taught thermodynamics concept using Artificial Intelligence-Enhanced Strategy and those exposed to lecture teaching method?

Table 1: Summary of the Results of Students' Posttest SPSS Score Mean and Standard Deviations for both the Experimental and Control Group

Groups	N	Mean	SD	SD Error	MD	Remarks
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(Impact of Artificial-Intelligence-Enhanced Strategy on Performance ... Yahaya, S. U... Et, al. 2025)

Experimental	77	29.15	9.12	2.43	7.07 Difference Exists
Control	63	22.08	8.75	2.13	
Total	140				

Table 1 revealed that the academic performance means scores for the experimental and control group was 29.15 and 22.08 respectively with the mean difference of 7.07. This means the experimental group achieved higher than the control group, and this can be attributed to the treatment. That is the use of Artificial Intelligence-Enhanced Strategy.

Research Question Two

What is gender interaction effect among Secondary School Students Performance in Thermodynamics concept?

Table 2: Summary of the Results of Students' Posttest SPSS Score Mean and Standard Deviations for both the Experimental Group by Gender.

Gender	N	Mean (X)	SD	Error	MD	Remark
Male	40	18.01	3.36	1.08	0.3	No difference
Female	37	17.98	3.64	1.12		
Total	77					

Table 2 presents data on the mean and standard deviation of the posttest scores of male and female students. The result obtained, there was no difference in the mean posttest scores of the male and female students taught using Artificial Intelligence Enhanced-Strategy. The male students mean score was 18.01 while that of the female was 17.98 with a mean difference of 0.3. This means that Artificial Intelligence-Enhanced Strategy is not gender friendly in teaching thermodynamics concept.

Hypothesis 1

There is no significant difference between the mean performance scores of students' taught thermodynamics concept using Artificial Intelligence-Enhanced Strategy and those exposed to lecture teaching method.

Table 3: Summary of One-way ANCOVA of Student Performance Score in SPS 1

Sources	Sum of Squares	DF	Mean Square	F	Sign.	Decision
Corrected Model	16245.594	5	3971.398	30.777*	.000	
Intercept	45745.732	2	45745.732	365.815*	.000	
Pre-test	32.0 60	2	33.0 60	0.280	.618	Not Sign.
AI Enhanced-Strategy	14669.230	1	14669.230	116.836*	0.07	Sign.
Error	14093.975	143	124.831			
Total	464685.000	163				
Corrected total	30239.576	169				

The result from Table 3 showed that 0.07 was obtained from the analysis which was greater than level of significance 0.05. Therefore, there is significance difference between the academic performances of students taught thermodynamics concept using Artificial Intelligence-Enhanced Strategy and those

(*Impact of Artificial-Intelligence-Enhanced Strategy on Performance ... Yahaya, S. U... Et, al. 2025*)

taught with teaching lecture method. This result indicated that teaching with Artificial Intelligence-Enhanced Strategy is effective in enhancing students' performance in thermodynamic concept.

Hypothesis 2

There is no significant difference between gender interaction effects among Secondary School Students Performance in Thermodynamics concept

Table 4: Summary of One-Way ANCOVA of Students' SPS Scores in SPSI by Gender

Sources	Square	Mean	DF	Mean Square	F	Significant	Decision
Corrected Model	16245.595		5	3811.398	30.777*	.000	
Intercept	45302.756		1	45302.745	365.815*	.000	
Pre-test	32.017		1	31.012	0.250	.618	Not Sign.
Gender	272.389		1	260.389	2.103	.150	Not Sign.
Error	13020.974		115	123.840			
Total	425685.000		119				
Corrected Total	29639.568		118				

Table 4 showed that there is no significance difference in the gender. Hence, the null hypothesis that said there is no significant difference between gender interaction effects among Secondary School Students Performance in Thermodynamics concept is rejected. Therefore, the Artificial Intelligence-Enhanced Strategy is a gender friendly in teaching thermodynamics concept.

Discussion of Findings

The findings of this study showed that there is significant difference in the level of performance between students taught thermodynamics concept using Artificial Intelligence-Enhanced Strategy and those taught with teaching lecture method. This finding is in line with Zudonu (2024) who conducted an investigating the effect of Artificial Intelligence in chemistry Students Performance and Conceptual Change in Heat Change in SSS 2 in Rivers State, Nigeria. The result showed that there is significant difference in academic performance between students who receive AI-based method and those who received traditional teaching method. They achieved equally well because of utilization of AI-based instruction. Another was conducted by Firas Almasri (2024) Systematic Review of Empirical Research about Exploring the Impact of Artificial Intelligence in Teaching and Learning of Science. The result showed that integrating Artificial Intelligence tools in chemistry education consistently improved students; academic performance. It was evident in higher test scores and a better understanding of complex concepts compared to those in traditional learning environments (Alneyadi & Wardat, 2023; Koć-Januchta *et al.*, 2020; Siddaway *et al.*, 2019).

The findings of this study also showed that there was no significant difference in the level of performance between male and female students taught Artificial Intelligence-Enhanced Strategy. This also agrees with the work of Bichi (2017) which showed no significant difference between male and female performance in chemistry. This result showed that Integrating Artificial Intelligence is a gender friendly.

Conclusion

(Impact of Artificial-Intelligence-Enhanced Strategy on Performance ... Yahaya, S. U... Et, al. 2025)

Based on the findings of this study, it was concluded that the use of Artificial Intelligence-Enhanced Strategy improved the student's academic performance on Thermodynamics concepts and its gender friendly at senior secondary school. In addition, the role of Artificial Intelligence technology is more over emphasis because it plays a vital role and it growing tremendously in the education sector.

Recommendations

The following recommendations were made base on the findings;

- i. It recommended that Chemistry teachers should adopt Artificial Intelligence-Enhanced Strategy to improve teaching and learning outcomes.
- ii. It also recommended the science teacher should be encouraged to use Artificial Intelligence-Enhanced Strategy in order to improve students' performance.

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